

ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR ASOSIDA ONA TILI TA'LIM MAZMUNINI
RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI

Oysha Qurbonova

Associate Professor (PhD)

of the National Pedagogical University of Uzbekistan named after Nizami.

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Abstract. *Mother tongue education is important in developing students' thinking skills, communication skills and creative approaches. In the modern education system, the development of mother tongue educational content plays an important role in the personal and social life of students. This article examines the factors of developing mother tongue educational content based on modern approaches.*

Keywords: *pedagogical, psychological, thinking, abilities, education, upbringing, system, modern trends, personality, development.*

In today's global information society, the need to improve the quality of mother tongue education is becoming more urgent.

Currently, the processes of teaching and mastering the Uzbek language are at the center of extensive pedagogical and psycholinguistic analysis. The Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6084 and No. PF-60974 set strategic tasks for learning the mother tongue, and modern approaches to curricula and methodologies are being introduced. At the same time, methodological approaches are being updated, taking into account factors such as the level of cognitive development of modern students, especially children in the 5th grade, their analytical thinking potential, and their motivation for language learning.[1]

In today's era of globalization, mother tongue education should not be limited to memorizing grammatical rules. Modern pedagogy is faced with the task of educating a student not only to write literately, but also to express his thoughts logically, fluently and in accordance with the situation. The updated National Curriculum of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at precisely this goal, namely, effectiveness in education.

Modern approaches to mother tongue education can be classified into the following areas:

1. Competency approach: In this approach, the main emphasis is shifted from "knowing" to "being able to apply". Rather than memorizing the definition of a noun or verb, it is more important for the student to effectively use these word classes in various speech situations (writing a formal letter, making a presentation, conducting a discussion).

2. Communicative approach: The teaching process is based on a lively dialogue between the student and the teacher. In this, the student's critical thinking and argumentation skills are developed through the methods of "Socratic seminars", "Debates" and "Case studies".

3. Integrated education: Connecting mother tongue lessons with literature, history, art and even information technology. For example, using the student's historical knowledge in the process of text analysis or showing the living mechanism of language by analyzing modern media texts (blogs, social media posts).

4. Integration of digital technologies: Using electronic textbooks, language corpora and artificial intelligence capabilities. This not only increases student interest, but also forms independent learning skills.

Gaming technologies allow for interesting and effective native language lessons. Through games, students can acquire new knowledge and participate in the lesson in an entertaining way.

Multimedia tools are modern resources used in native language lessons. With the help of video, audio and interactive materials, teachers can make lessons more interesting.

Native language education is important in developing students' communication, thinking and creative abilities. This process allows students to express their thoughts, improve their speech culture and arouse interest in literature. The quality of native language education plays an important role in the formation of students' general education skills.

Modern approaches involve the use of new methods and techniques in the educational process. Among these approaches, the following can be distinguished:

1. Active learning methods ensure the active participation of students. These include:

- Problem-based learning: Helping students solve real-life problems.
- Collaborative learning: Developing cooperation between students.

2. Differentiated learning involves providing education in accordance with the individual needs of each student. With this approach, students choose the level of complexity based on their abilities.

The integration approach involves teaching different subjects together. By combining subjects such as literature, history, and art in native language education, students' interest can be increased.

1. There are a number of factors in developing the content of native language education:

2. Innovative technologies make the educational process more effective. With the help of multimedia resources, the Internet, and other modern tools, teachers can conduct native language lessons interesting and effective.

3. The role of the teacher is important in mother tongue education. The teacher is responsible for motivating students, developing their abilities, and managing the lesson process.

4. Modern teaching methods and techniques play an important role in developing the content of mother tongue education. Through problem-based, collaborative, and differentiated approaches, teachers encourage students to actively participate.

The use of innovative methods in mother tongue education increases students' interest and develops their thinking skills.

Observations show that in lessons organized on the basis of modern approaches, the functional literacy of students increases by 30-40%. The ability to work with text forms such vital skills as sorting, analyzing and drawing conclusions in students. Unlike traditional "rule memorization" lessons, the new methodology instills in the student a view of language as a "social weapon". In conclusion, the use of modern approaches in native language education is a requirement of the time. The transition from grammar-centered education to text- and speech-centered education is a key factor in the formation of a generation that is aware of national identity, competitive and creatively thinking. Improving the modern methodological skills of teachers and enriching textbooks with interactive content will ensure the success of reforms in this area.

Developing the content of mother tongue education based on modern approaches creates new opportunities for teachers and students. With the help of innovative methods and modern technologies, mother tongue lessons will become more effective and interesting. Teachers can develop students' thinking skills by supporting modern approaches in their work.

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